

The Next Big Questions in Loneliness Research

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Maike Luhmann ¹

Libor Potočár ²

Yeeun Archer Lee ³

Fredrica Nyqvist ⁴

Pauline Kleinschlömer ⁵

Pamela Qualter ⁶

Hans Rocha IJzerman ⁷

Mathias Lasgaard ⁸

Author Affiliations

¹ Ruhr University Bochum, Germany, and German Center for Mental Health (DZPG), Bochum/Marburg site.

² PROMENTA Research Center, Department of Psychology, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway.

³ Department of Psychology, Trinity Western University, Langley, Canada.

⁴ Department of Natural and Health Sciences, Åbo Akademi University, Finland.

⁵ Federal Institute for Population Research, Wiesbaden, Germany.

⁶ Manchester Institute of Education, University of Manchester, Manchester, United Kingdom.

⁷ Annecy Behavioral Science Lab, Saint-Jorioz, France, Entrelacs, Saint-Jorioz, France, and University of Oxford, Oxford Internet Institute, Oxford, United Kingdom.

⁸ Department of Psychology, University of Southern Denmark, Esbjerg, Denmark; DEFACTUM – Public Health Research, Central Denmark Region, Aarhus, Denmark.

Corresponding Author Contact

Maike Luhmann, Ruhr University Bochum, maike.luhmann@rub.de

CRediT Author Statement

The order of the authorship for all co-authors was determined randomly.

Individual contributions were as follows: **Maike Luhmann**: Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing, Funding acquisition. **Libor Potočár**: Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. **Yeeun Archer Lee**: Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. **Fredrica Nyqvist**: Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. **Pauline Kleinschlömer**: Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. **Pamela Qualter**: Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. **Hans Rocha IJzerman**: Conceptualization, Writing – Original Draft, Writing – Review & Editing. **Mathias Lasgaard**: Writing – Review & Editing.

Conflicts of Interest

Hans Rocha IJzerman declares the following potential conflicts of interest: He is the founder and CEO of Entrelacs, a company developing AI-powered mental-health assessment tools. He is also Director of the Annecy Behavioral Science Lab (ABSL), a company which receives grant funding for loneliness-adjacent research.

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Executive Summary

Background

Loneliness is increasingly recognized as a policy issue in many countries. However, although loneliness research is booming, the produced research is not always immediately relevant for policymakers aspiring to develop evidence-based policies to reduce loneliness. Based on the results of a symposium bringing together researchers, policymakers and other non-academics, this paper identifies and prioritizes those research questions that matter to researchers across disciplines and to policymakers and other decision makers alike.

Priority Area 1: Improving the Conceptualization and Measurement of Loneliness

A central challenge to loneliness research is that current measurement approaches are fragmented and insufficiently validated across diverse contexts, partly because of a more general disagreement on how loneliness should be defined. To improve the conceptualization and measurement of loneliness, we propose the following:

1. Refine the *conceptualization of loneliness* by clearly distinguishing different forms of loneliness, including loneliness referring to different types of social connections (e.g., emotional vs. social vs. existential loneliness), different temporal facets of loneliness (e.g., transient vs. chronic loneliness), and different levels of intensity.
2. Develop *defendable cutoffs* to distinguish between those who are (more) lonely and those who are not (or less) lonely to harmonize the estimation of prevalence rates and time trends.
3. Test and improve the *cross-cultural applicability and sensitivity* of loneliness measures so that loneliness can be measured in a way that is comparable across languages and cultures.
4. Develop *alternative approaches to the measurement of loneliness*, including personalized measurement and alternative data sources such as passive mobile sensing data.

Priority Area 2: Towards a Comprehensive Understanding of Risk Factors

Decades of research have established that certain groups of people consistently report higher prevalence of loneliness. The pressing open question is not only *who* is lonely, but *why* certain groups experience higher levels of loneliness than others, and under what social, cultural, and structural conditions these differences emerge. Specifically, we propose to prioritize the following issues:

1. Adopt an ***intersectional approach*** to describe and explain how the accumulation of overlapping and mutually reinforcing disadvantages can exacerbate the loneliness risk.
2. Understanding the ***pathways*** toward loneliness and ***mechanisms*** behind severe loneliness to inform the development of more precise and effective interventions.
3. Move beyond individual-level analysis to understand how macro-level factors such as ***social, physical, and structural conditions*** shape the experience and distribution of loneliness.
4. Expand research on the impact of current and future ***societal macro trends*** such as digitalization and social media, artificial intelligence, and other emerging risks on loneliness.

Priority Area 3: Understanding the Impacts of Loneliness on Individuals and Societies

While the negative effects of loneliness on health and longevity are well established, the causal pathways linking loneliness and health and the impact of loneliness on individuals and societies beyond health are less well understood. We propose to prioritize the following topics:

1. Understand ***at what point loneliness starts to have negative impacts*** and identify the threshold at which it shifts from a transient, potentially adaptive experience to a chronic condition with pathological consequences.
2. Understand the ***causal pathways*** that link loneliness with impaired health, reduced productivity, and a range of other individual and societal outcomes, and consider possible bidirectional relationships between loneliness and its outcomes.
3. Understand how loneliness can be passed on ***from one generation to the next***.

Priority Area 4: Develop Interventions that Reduce Loneliness Effectively

Although there have been growing efforts to systematically evaluate loneliness interventions, the current evidence base remains insufficient to provide a unified understanding of what works for whom (and what does not) across diverse populations and contexts. We propose to prioritize the following topics:

1. Understand ***what kind of interventions work for whom and why*** to inform the development on targeted and personalized interventions.
2. Compare the effectiveness of ***universal, population-wide initiatives*** versus ***targeted programmes*** designed for particular groups.

3. Estimate the *cost-effectiveness of interventions* and consider “use cases” to help practitioners determine the relative value of implementing specific interventions for different populations.
4. Study the *long-term effects of interventions*.
5. *Identify what does not work*, for example, interventions that are ineffective for specific groups or that have unintended side effects that could be counterproductive and harmful.

Implications for Loneliness Research

Addressing the big questions raised above requires changing the way researchers study loneliness:

1. Loneliness researchers need *more and better data* on loneliness by implementing studies with smart research designs, valid and culturally sensitive measures, and bigger and more representative and diverse samples.
2. Loneliness researchers need to systematically foster *interdisciplinary and international collaborations* that include researchers from all continents.
3. Loneliness researchers should *make their research useable* for policymakers and other decision makers.

Introduction

Loneliness research is booming. According to Web of Science, the annual number of scientific publications on loneliness has increased from 707 (2015) to 3908 (2024), amounting to an increase of about 500 percent over ten years. Over the same period, loneliness has also been increasingly recognized as a policy issue (Goldman et al., 2026; Goldman et al., 2024) and has been picked up by cross-national institutions such as the World Health Organization (WHO Commission on Social Connection, 2025).

The widespread attention to loneliness has been fuelled by research showing that loneliness can have substantial negative effects on individuals and societies. People experiencing loneliness have an increased risk of developing various illnesses, ranging from cardiovascular diseases to diabetes to dementia to early mortality (Park et al., 2020), making loneliness a public health challenge (e.g., WHO Commission on Social Connection, 2025) with downstream negative effects on economic prosperity (L. Engel et al., 2025). But the negative consequences of loneliness do not stop there: Recent research shows that people reporting loneliness are more likely to distrust other people and institutions and more susceptible to conspiracy beliefs and non-democratic political attitudes (Langenkamp, 2025). Although this line of research is still in its early stages, it suggests that widespread loneliness might be a risk factor for democracy (Hertz, 2020).

These research findings have caught the attention of policymakers and initiated the development of political strategies against loneliness in multiple countries such as the Denmark, France, Germany, Japan, the Netherlands, Spain, and the United Kingdom (Goldman et al., 2026; Goldman et al., 2024; Wendt, 2024). Most of these strategies were developed with scientific input. For example, Germany's federal strategy was shaped by the *Kompetenznetz Einsamkeit*, which actively engaged researchers to ensure policies were grounded in empirical evidence; the same can be said of the relationship between the Department for Culture, Media, and Sport, who lead England's Tackling Loneliness initiative, and leading researchers of loneliness in the UK. Similarly, a national policy and action plan in Denmark has been informed by detailed population-level data on loneliness provided by researchers.

However, a common challenge in these processes is that the available scientific evidence does not always align with the needs of policymakers developing political solutions. For instance, many programmes aimed at supporting people reporting loneliness have not undergone rigorous scientific evaluation, leaving their effectiveness based largely on anecdotal reports. Similarly, there is a notable absence of empirical studies focused on the effectiveness of interventions targeting specific high-risk groups, such as LGBTQ+ people, single-parent households, adolescents, people with chronic illnesses, or residents of nursing institutions.

One reason for the lack of policy-relevant evidence may be that researchers and policymakers diverge in which questions about loneliness they think are particularly relevant. Researchers typically prioritize questions that are conceptually interesting within their academic field, or they focus on addressing specific empirical gaps, which, while important, may not always align with the needs of policymakers working on political solutions. In addition, some of the questions that policymakers are particularly interested in are difficult to examine empirically. As a result, the produced research is not always immediately relevant for policymakers.

We want to stress that we neither believe nor demand that all research efforts should be aligned with current policy needs. Many innovative ideas are rooted in basic research that was driven by the expertise and curiosity of researchers, and not commissioned by governmental or non-governmental sponsors. However, we believe there is substantial overlap between the questions that matter to researchers across disciplines and those that matter to policymakers and other non-academics. To identify and prioritize those questions, it is necessary to bring the different parties to the same table. This paper is the outcome of such an exercise.

In this paper, we describe what we have identified as the most important next big questions for loneliness research. We, that is not only the authors of this paper, but all fifty participants of a three-day symposium on loneliness that took place in Hannover, Germany, in June 2025 and that was funded by the Volkswagen Foundation. The detailed program, presentations and a list of all active participants are available at <https://osf.io/s3fw6>. The symposium brought together researchers from various countries, disciplines, and career levels, and policymakers and other non-academics to discuss current and future research on four broad topics: (1) standards for measuring and monitoring loneliness, (2) risk groups and predictors of loneliness, (3) individual and societal impacts of loneliness, and (4) solutions to reduce loneliness effectively. Central to the symposium were workshops in which all participants were invited to identify and prioritize the next big questions within each of these topics. This paper builds on those workshops by elaborating on the challenges and research questions identified as highly relevant by both researchers and policymakers, and by discussing their implications for future loneliness research.

Improving the Conceptualization and Measurement of Loneliness

A central challenge to loneliness research is that current measurement approaches are fragmented and insufficiently validated across diverse contexts. Current approaches to measure loneliness can best be characterized as a “measurement tower of Babel” (Fisher, 2000; E. I. Fried, 2017): tools range from single-item proxies to 20-item legacy scales, with wide variation in how loneliness is measured across studies and countries (Mahony et al., 2024). This variability in measurements is at least partly a consequence of a more general disagreement on how loneliness should be defined. According to one of the most common definitions of loneliness, people experience loneliness when their social needs and their expectations for social relationships are not met by their actual social relationships (Peplau & Perlman, 1982). However, while this general definition is widely accepted, loneliness researchers disagree on whether and how many different forms of loneliness should be distinguished, and the wide range of available measurement approaches reflects these different positions. In addition, most measurement approaches have been developed in high-income countries and lack cross-cultural applicability. In this section, we elaborate on these points and discuss novel, innovative alternatives to traditional measurement approaches.

Distinguishing Different Forms of Loneliness

In large-scale surveys, loneliness is often measured with a single item such as, “How much of the time, during the past four weeks, have you been feeling lonely?” (Mauri et al., 2024). Such a measurement approach implicitly assumes that loneliness is a unidimensional construct. Multidimensional approaches, in contrast, assume that loneliness can be differentiated into different facets or forms based on, for example, the types of social connections that people are missing (Table 1). The most common distinction is the one between emotional and social loneliness, originally proposed by Weiss (1973) and operationalized in the widely used scale by de Jong Gierveld and van Tilburg (2006). However, some researchers argue that this conceptualization is too narrow and should be expanded to include additional forms of loneliness such as collective loneliness (Hawkley et al., 2005), cultural loneliness (van Staden & Coetzee, 2010), physical loneliness (Landmann & Rohmann, 2022), existential loneliness (Ettema et al., 2010; McKenna-Plumley et al., 2023) or other facets, to ensure that the definition of loneliness captures the entire range of lived experiences of people around the globe (Akhter-Khan et al., 2024). This is also evident across age groups, with different aspects of loneliness being particularly salient at different stages of the life course (Qualter et al., 2025; Verity et al., 2025).

Table 1. Different forms of loneliness according to the type of social connection they perceive as lacking

Form of loneliness	Description
Emotional loneliness	Lack of a close, intimate relationship or a person who one can trust completely
Social loneliness	Lack of good relationships with friends or families or a greater social network
Collective loneliness	Lack of connection to a broader community or to society as a whole
Cultural loneliness	Absence of one's preferred cultural or linguistic environment
Physical loneliness	Lack of physical closeness
Existential loneliness	Awareness of one's fundamental separateness as a human being

In addition, one can distinguish different temporal facets of loneliness. For example, the distinction between state and trait loneliness acknowledges that individuals' momentary (state) experiences of loneliness fluctuate over time, but tend to vary around a relatively stable baseline that reflects a person's trait level of loneliness (Mund et al., 2025; van Roekel et al., 2018). A related approach differentiates between transient (or episodic), situational, and chronic loneliness (Young, 1982). These categories are typically used to describe differences in the duration of loneliness (with transient loneliness being short-lived, and chronic loneliness persisting over extended periods), and its presumed triggers (situational loneliness is assumed to be linked to identifiable external events, such as a relocation, to which individuals are expected to adapt over time).

However, closer inspection reveals limited consensus in the literature regarding how those temporal forms of loneliness should be defined and operationalized (Conneely et al., 2025). This lack of clarity is particularly problematic for chronic loneliness, which is often defined in terms of prolonged duration. Emerging evidence suggests, however, that severity (intensity of the emotions) – not only duration – may be critical, because more severe forms of loneliness are associated with greater negative health consequences (Martín-María et al., 2020; Misiak et al., 2025; Oughli & Lee, 2024). Although severe loneliness is frequently equated with chronic or prolonged loneliness (Conneely et al., 2025), severity may also be conceptualised in terms of the frequency of lonely experiences (i.e., how often loneliness is felt) and their intensity (i.e., how strong or distressing those feelings are) (Weiss, 1973). Indeed, some research suggests that severe loneliness is best captured by considering duration, frequency, and intensity simultaneously (Conneely et al., 2025; Qualter et al., 2021). Despite that, widely used loneliness measures, such as the UCLA Loneliness Scale (Russell, 1996), primarily assess frequency and do not explicitly capture the intensity or duration of loneliness experiences.

In sum, there is a clear need to build consensus on the conceptualization of loneliness and its different forms, facets and manifestations, and use this as a basis to develop novel

measures of loneliness that allow a reliable, valid and culturally sensitive operationalization of loneliness. One way forward is to initiate a systematic consensus building process that involves experts from multiple disciplines and backgrounds to ensure that diverse perspectives on this topic are included (for examples and a roadmap, see Leising et al., 2024). Such a process could be organized by international working groups whose members combine theoretical knowledge, measurement expertise, ethnographic insights, and lived experience across different cultural contexts.

Who Counts as (Severely) Lonely? Developing Defendable Cutoffs

Loneliness is not a binary state: One is not either lonely or not. Rather, individual differences in loneliness are best represented on a continuum, and we generally recommend treating loneliness as a continuous variable in empirical research. However, it is sometimes useful to distinguish between those who are (more) lonely and those who are not (or less) lonely. For example, distinguishing between groups of people who report loneliness and those who do not is necessary to estimate the prevalence of loneliness in a specific population. Prevalence rates that reflect the percentage of people experiencing loneliness are often easier to understand and to communicate than average scores on some loneliness scale, particularly in non-academic contexts. A statement such as 13 percent of Europeans feel lonely (Mauri et al., 2024) is much more useful to convey the gravity of the problem than a statement such as, “European’s average loneliness levels is 4.9 on a scale from 3 to 9.”

Classifying people requires determining a threshold (e.g., a specific cutoff score on a scale) that distinguishes those whose loneliness requires support from those whose loneliness does not. Currently, however, there is a great variability in how thresholds are chosen, not just across different scales, but even across studies using the same scale (Conneely et al., 2025). As a result, prevalence estimates are hard or even impossible to compare across studies and populations. The lack of a consensus on a threshold is again reflective of the lack of a proper conceptualization of what constitutes severe loneliness (see previous section).

What makes a cutoff defendable? The current more-or-less arbitrary selection of thresholds is certainly the least defendable option. Finding a consensus on a common threshold (e.g., as part of the consensus building process mentioned previously) is better, but only if this threshold has a theoretical or empirical foundation. The Evolutionary Theory of Loneliness (Cacioppo & Cacioppo, 2018; Cacioppo & Hawkley, 2009; Qualter et al., 2015) might provide such a theoretical foundation because it suggests that some people can get stuck in a negative loop of maladaptive cognitions and behaviours that reinforces their social isolation and loneliness (see below). Distinguishing between those who are not yet stuck in this loop, and those who are, would provide a theory-based classification. However, as we will see

later, how exactly people become stuck in this loop, and how this can be assessed, is not yet completely understood.

A defensible cutoff could also be based on empirical findings. For instance, if studies could identify a certain level of severity that determines whether loneliness is likely to be associated with some external criterion (e.g., certain health issues), this level could be used as an empirically determined cutoff to distinguish between people who feel lonely and those who do not. However, although there have been attempts to find that among youth (Qualter et al., 2013) and young adults (Bangee et al., 2014), whether such a discrete tipping point exists is doubtful. And even if it does, its location on the loneliness severity spectrum might vary across individuals and cultural contexts (see next section). Overall, whether and how people should be categorized according to their reported levels of loneliness is one of the biggest unresolved challenges in this field.

Cross-Cultural Applicability and Sensitivity of Loneliness Measures

A large body of research suggests that loneliness measures are reliable and valid (Maes et al., 2022; Mund et al., 2023), but investigations of their cross-cultural applicability and sensitivity are scarcer. At a time when loneliness is increasingly recognized as a worldwide challenge (WHO Commission on Social Connection, 2025) and loneliness research is becoming increasingly global, loneliness must be measured in a way that is applicable and comparable across languages and cultures.

Cross-cultural research examining the psychometric properties of the most widely used measures of loneliness – the De Jong Gierveld Scale and the UCLA Loneliness Scale – demonstrates their validity and reliability and suggests a similar dimensional structure across multiple countries around the globe (Alsubheen et al., 2021; de Jong Gierveld & van Tilburg, 2010; Hudiyana et al., 2022). This indicates that the fundamental experience of loneliness may be largely shared across various cultures. However, these systematic investigations sometimes failed to demonstrate metric and scalar scale invariance (Hudiyana et al., 2022), suggesting that the way loneliness is experienced and expressed may vary across countries. For example, a recent psychometric evaluation of data from 27 European Union countries found that while the 3-Item UCLA Loneliness Scale showed scalar invariance across all EU countries (but showed limited content validity), the 6-item De Jong Gierveld Loneliness Scale achieved scalar invariance only within specific country clusters (but with better content validity), and single-item measures showed sufficient construct validity in 19 of 27 countries (Paris et al., 2025).

Combined, this psychometric evidence underscores the need to further develop culturally sensitive measures which would allow for valid cross-country comparisons, pivotal to effective policymaking at an international level.

Alternative Approaches to the Measurement of Loneliness

Standardized self-report questionnaires have many well-known strengths, but they are not perfect. Two limitations that apply to most self-report questionnaires – including but not limited to those measuring loneliness – require particular attention.

First, any attempt to measure a psychological experience with a few standardized items completed at a single random timepoint imposes a necessarily narrow operationalization of this experience upon all participants, and thereby risks omitting any idiosyncratic variability in people’s experiences (Kuper et al., 2025). Two persons with a similar score on a standardized loneliness scale may differ in how they experience loneliness (loneliness symptoms), what causes their loneliness (predictors) and how they cope with these experiences (consequences). Moreover, these unique patterns can differ not only between, but even within people, shifting with context and time. Capturing such unique dynamic processes requires a personalized (idiographic) measurement approach, for example by collecting narrative and/or intensive longitudinal data. Intensive longitudinal data is particularly suitable to describe intraindividual, contextualized dynamics in loneliness that have already been shown to be predictive of future loneliness and psychopathological symptoms (Beck & Jackson, 2022; Buecker et al., 2024). In addition, analyzing such data with psychometric network models can identify “ergodic subgroups” – clusters of individuals who share similar symptom structures – within which group-level findings generalize more meaningfully (Golino et al., 2025; Kaiser et al., 2025). Personalized measurement approaches may also provide a solution to the challenge of defensible cutoffs for loneliness (see above). Instead of using poorly defined one-size-fits-all cutoffs, idiographic approaches allow developing dynamic models of loneliness that provide individual or group-specific baselines against which the current loneliness experiences can be evaluated.

Second, people’s self-reports can be biased in several ways. Some of these biases are already known in the loneliness literature; for example, some studies suggest that people (particularly men) respond differently when asked directly about their loneliness experiences rather than indirectly in a way that avoids that term, presumably because experiencing loneliness is still stigmatized in some populations (Barreto et al., 2022; Shiovitz-Ezra & Ayalon, 2012). Responses may also differ depending on the mode of assessment, for example, people often report more socially desirable or less negative information in face-to-face interviews than in online or written surveys, likely due to interviewer presence and greater concern about stigma or social evaluation (Stegen et al., 2024). It is also possible that people lack self-knowledge to provide accurate assessments; or that they intentionally misreport their actual experiences. These limitations are again not unique to loneliness but apply to all self-reports of psychological experiences. A solution to this problem is to augment self-reports with data from other sources such as other people (i.e., informant reports) or observable behaviors. For example, eye-tracking of social stimuli can provide information on attention

biases (Bangee et al., 2014; Qualter et al., 2013), and passive mobile sensing through smartphones and wearables can provide behavioral indicators on mobility patterns, communication rhythms, sleep regularity, and physical activity (Harari & Gosling, 2023). When combined with psychological measures, such indicators have been reported to predict daily loneliness with some accuracy in some studies (Doryab et al., 2019; for a critical review, see Qirtas et al., 2022).

In sum, neither personalized measurement nor behavioral data can or should completely replace standardized self-reports, but they can provide additional information that can potentially improve the identification of who is lonely, especially if used in combination.

Towards a Comprehensive Understanding of Risk Factors and Risk Groups

Loneliness is a universal human experience, yet its burden is not distributed evenly across society. Decades of research have established that certain groups of people consistently report higher prevalence of loneliness, often due to biological, psychological, social, or economic vulnerabilities. For example, individuals who are single, unemployed, or living with adverse mental or physical health conditions are at greater risk. Similarly, those with a migration background, minority status, or personality traits such as high neuroticism have been shown to be disproportionately affected (for review, see Barjaková et al., 2023).

While this work has been critical in mapping loneliness and its correlates, the next frontier lies in moving beyond description. The pressing open question is not only *who* is lonely, but *why* certain groups experience higher levels of loneliness than others, and under what social, cultural, and structural conditions these differences emerge.

Understanding these mechanisms is crucial for informing the design of interventions, particularly in evaluating whether targeted approaches, tailored to specific risk profiles, or general strategies, aimed at broader population, are more effective. However, risk factors for loneliness rarely exist in isolation: They are dynamic, interdependent, and often shaped by broader societal trends such as aging populations, digitalization, changing family structures, and socioeconomic inequalities. Addressing these complexities requires a comprehensive interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral approach, engaging diverse academic fields and societal actors.

In the following sections, we outline key avenues for future research by highlighting open questions regarding loneliness risk factors and high-risk populations. By doing so, we aim to shift the conversation from documenting prevalence and at-risk groups toward a deeper understanding of mechanisms, pathways, and solutions.

When Risks Coincide: Adopting an Intersectional Approach to Risk Factors

It is well established that marginalized groups are more likely to experience loneliness than majority populations, yet emerging research shows that loneliness is rarely attributable to a single factor (Li & Spini, 2022; Yang, 2023). Instead, it often arises from the accumulation of overlapping disadvantages that reinforce each other and limit access to support. Poor health, poverty, and migration background are each known to elevate the risk of loneliness (e.g., Barjaková et al., 2023), but when these risks coincide, they may intensify their impact. For instance, people with a migration background are more likely to experience poverty (Smalen et al., 2024) and face barriers to healthcare (Castañeda et al., 2015; Hossin, 2020), which in turn heightens their risk of loneliness. Structural inequalities may further exacerbate these risks: Discriminatory policies, ageism, inaccessible public spaces, and digital exclusion can systematically limit opportunities for social connection and participation (Aartsen et al., 2025; Barreto et al., 2021).

These dynamics highlight the importance of an intersectional approach that considers how different identities and systemic barriers interact to shape experiences of loneliness. Such an approach should guide research, but also inform the design of interventions, ensuring they are culturally sensitive, contextually relevant, and inclusive of diverse lived experiences (e.g., Welch et al., 2024). A sharper focus on individuals facing multiple, overlapping risks is both ethically necessary and strategically important. It enables earlier identification of those most vulnerable, supports more targeted prevention efforts, and contributes to the development of fairer, more socially just policies.

Understanding Pathways Toward Loneliness

Loneliness is not a static experience but a dynamic process, with pathways into and out of loneliness varying across individuals, social groups, and contexts. Understanding these trajectories and the mechanisms driving them is essential for developing more precise and effective interventions. Established theoretical perspectives conceptualize loneliness as an adaptive, transient signal that activates the motivation to reconnect with others (Cacioppo et al., 2014; Qualter et al., 2015). While motivating us to restore our social bonds, loneliness can also increase our sensitivity to social threats and signals, such as rejection, and various cognitive biases, including better recall of negative social events (Cacioppo & Hawkley, 2009; Hawkley & Cacioppo, 2010; Qualter et al., 2015). In turn, these processes can lead to increased social withdrawal, creating a vicious circle – or a self-fulfilling prophecy – in which loneliness breeds perceptions, behaviours, and feelings that effectively perpetuate loneliness (Cacioppo & Hawkley, 2009; Hawkley & Cacioppo, 2010; Qualter et al., 2015). Becoming lonely is, therefore, not the same as remaining lonely: While some individuals recover quickly, others remain lonely despite facing similar external conditions; those with

limited resources or compounded disadvantages who may struggle to overcome isolation without external support may be particularly vulnerable to getting ‘stuck in’ loneliness.

Although these theoretical frameworks are informed by empirical research (Qualter et al., 2015; Spithoven et al., 2017), the concrete pathways through which some people enter the negative cycle and others do not remain poorly understood. Additionally, future research must also examine whether specific forms of loneliness (see Table 1) are driven by distinct factors, and whether these mechanisms vary across subgroups. Progress in this area will require longitudinal and causal research designs, supported by advanced statistical techniques capable of tracking transitions over time. Uncovering mediating and moderating factors will shed light on why some individuals are more likely to become lonely – or less able to recover – than others. Complementary qualitative research is also needed to capture the lived experiences of loneliness, explore subjective meanings, and understand how individuals navigate and make sense of their social worlds.

The Role of Meso- and Macro-Level Factors in Shaping Loneliness

Another critical frontier in loneliness research concerns how broader social, physical, and structural conditions shape the experience and distribution of loneliness, highlighting the need to move beyond individual-level analysis (Huxhold et al., 2022; Nyqvist, Power, & Coll-Planas, 2025). This requires greater attention to systemic contributors operating at both the meso and macro levels (Nyqvist, Power, & Coll-Planas, 2025). At the meso level, community-based factors such as neighbourhood dynamics, social cohesion, access to social infrastructure (e.g., parks, libraries, community centres), and the presence and quality of local organizations, schools and workplaces are central. At the macro level, broader societal and structural conditions, including urban planning and the built environment (e.g., housing density, walkability), socioeconomic inequality and segregation, welfare systems and public policies, cultural norms around family roles and independence, as well as systemic discrimination such as racism and ageism can profoundly shape loneliness. At present, loneliness research remains heavily concentrated in industrialized, Western contexts (Surkalim et al., 2022; WHO Commission on Social Connection, 2025), limiting insight into how structural and contextual forces operate globally. Addressing these gaps will require broader and more globally representative data collection, using standardized measurement tools that enable meaningful comparison across contexts and populations.

By moving beyond individual-level explanations to meso- and macro-level determinants, research can uncover upstream drivers of loneliness and inform the development of structural interventions, such as inclusive urban design and investment in social infrastructure, that offer more sustainable, population-level impact. This shift also reframes loneliness not as an individual shortcoming but as a reflection of structural inequalities (Barreto et al., 2024), thereby opening new pathways for socially just, population-level solutions.

The Role of Social Media, AI, and Other Macro Trends

Digital technologies – particularly social media and emerging AI tools – are now deeply embedded in everyday life, especially among younger generations. Their influence on loneliness remains highly ambivalent: while these platforms can foster meaningful connection and support, they can also intensify isolation, depending on factors such as platform design (Matthews et al., 2025) or usage patterns (Nowland et al., 2018; Roberts et al., 2024). As digital environments evolve at unprecedented speed, there is an urgent need to critically assess their psychological and social consequences, and to evaluate under which circumstances they mitigate or exacerbate loneliness. For example, whether social media use is associated with increased or decreased loneliness appears to depend on the particular platform, how frequently and how actively or passively the platform is used, and the age of the users (Blasko & Castelli, 2022). Whether AI-powered chatbots, social robots or other digital tools could harm or benefit people might similarly depend on how and why people use them (Grey et al., 2024; Welch et al., 2023).

Beyond the digital sphere, a wider set of global risks, including climate change, wars, and pandemics, also threatens social connectedness (Kwamie et al., 2024). Climate change, in particular, is increasingly recognized as a structural risk factor for loneliness: extreme weather events, displacement, and environmental degradation can disrupt community ties, especially among older adults, low-income populations, and rural communities (Ayalon, 2025). At the same time, the psychological burden of climate anxiety may contribute to feelings of disconnection, particularly among younger people confronted with an uncertain future (Hajek & König, 2022).

Taken together, these digital and environmental transformations underscore the need for research that anticipates how new technologies and global crises may intersect to reshape the landscape of loneliness. Such work will be essential to inform timely and adaptive interventions that safeguard social connectedness in rapidly changing social and ecological contexts.

Understanding the Impacts of Loneliness on Individuals and Societies

There is vast evidence showing that loneliness is prospectively associated with mental health problems and lowered well-being, particularly depression (Hilliard et al., 2024; Leigh-Hunt et al., 2017; Mann et al., 2022; Park et al., 2020), deteriorated physical health, including an increased risk of cardiovascular disease and dementia (Park et al., 2020; Valtorta et al., 2016), and premature mortality (HaGani et al., 2025; Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015; Leigh-Hunt et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2023). Moreover, emerging evidence suggests that

loneliness is linked to educational difficulties (Matthews et al., 2023), unemployment, disability, and lower income (Matthews et al., 2019; Soest et al., 2020), right-extreme and antifeminist attitudes (Langenkamp, 2025), and lower voting turnout and political disengagement (Langenkamp, 2021a, 2021b). Combined, loneliness-related healthcare costs and productivity losses constitute economic burden for societies (L. Engel et al., 2025) and loneliness may also pose a potential threat to democracies around the globe.

However, the evidence on the strength and direction of a causal link between loneliness and physical health outcomes is inconsistent (Hilliard et al., 2024; Hong et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2025; Liang et al., 2024), warranting an application of diverse causal inference approaches. Moreover, a more comprehensive examination of multiple domains beyond health – including education, labour market, family-related, and political outcomes – is needed. For example, there is increasing evidence that loneliness might be linked to a greater risk for political radicalization (Langenkamp, 2025), but to date, this link has been investigated in only a few high-quality studies. Also, a more nuanced understanding of how loneliness relates to the onset, development, course, and maintenance of various individual-level and societal outcomes, including the underlying mechanisms, is warranted. Finally, most previous research on the consequences of loneliness has overlooked a potential dynamic interplay between loneliness and its consequences, highlighting the importance of examining whether and how loneliness and its outcomes co-develop and influence each other over time. Combined, these efforts will be essential for informing policies that aim to reduce social inequalities and strengthen population well-being across the life course. For future research, the questions and topics described next are of particular importance.

At What Point Does Loneliness Start to Have Negative Impacts?

As discussed earlier, loneliness experiences can trigger a negative cycle through which loneliness becomes chronic. These chronic and severe feelings of loneliness, in turn, have substantial negative consequences on health and other life domains (Hawkley & Cacioppo, 2010). To prevent these negative consequences (e.g., via effective loneliness interventions), it is important to determine when exactly loneliness begins to exert harmful effects on mental and physical health, and to identify the threshold at which it shifts from a transient, potentially adaptive experience to a chronic condition with pathological consequences. Differentiating between normative, transient loneliness and severe, chronic loneliness is critical to avoid over-pathologizing a common emotional experience. Identifying such a threshold could also inform efforts to develop defensible cutoffs for loneliness (see above). Some research suggests that the duration of loneliness might matter more than its intensity or frequency (Conneely et al., 2025), but overall, research on this question is still scarce and largely relies on cross-sectional self-report data, which cannot be used to study how loneliness and its outcomes are linked over time – a problem that does not only concern this particular question, as we discuss next.

Understanding the Causal Effects of Loneliness

As described, loneliness is associated with impaired health, reduced productivity, and a range of other individual and societal outcomes. But does this mean that loneliness *causes* those outcomes, either directly or indirectly? Most studies in this field are unable to answer this question because they rely on study designs that are not suited for causal conclusions. There are several reasons why we need to develop a better understanding of the causal effects of loneliness. First, understanding the mechanisms through which loneliness influences outcomes is essential for the design and implementation of effective interventions. Without this knowledge, efforts to mitigate the negative impacts of loneliness may be misdirected or ineffective. For example, banning social media for teenagers, as it is currently discussed or already implemented in countries such as Australia, France, or Germany, would only effectively reduce loneliness among teenagers if social media use has, indeed, a causal negative effect on loneliness. Second, the recognition of loneliness as a societally relevant issue hinges, at least in part, on the premise that loneliness has a detrimental impact on public health and other significant outcomes. Understanding the causal mechanisms underlying this link is crucial for validating these claims and justifying the allocation of resources towards addressing loneliness as a public health concern.

How can this be achieved? Study designs such as experiments or randomized-controlled trials that use randomization and manipulation of the independent variable are considered the gold standard to investigate causal links between variables. These kinds of designs are hardly used in research on loneliness and its individual and societal outcomes – for two understandable reasons: It would be ethically questionable to randomly make some people severely lonely (and others not) and unfeasible to then track their health over long timespans. However, experiments and randomized controlled trials are not the only approaches to examine causal inference, as we discuss later. In short, to improve our causal understanding of the impacts of loneliness, we need to implement robust causal study designs formulated within the causal inference frameworks (Bailey et al., 2024).

In addition, future work should also consider that the causal relationship can be bidirectional, resulting in a dynamic co-development of loneliness and its outcomes over time. For example, poor health is known to be both a risk factor and an outcome of loneliness. Such dynamic, bidirectional relationships are not limited to health but can include other biological and psychosocial factors and an individual's broader social environment. Conceptually, future work would benefit from reliance on theoretical frameworks that consider such complex, multi-level, dynamic interactions, for example, socio-ecological (Bronfenbrenner, 1977), bio-psycho-social (G. L. Engel, 1977), and eco-social (Krieger, 2001) frameworks. Methodologically, approaches such as Mendelian randomization (Hilliard et al., 2024; Liang et al., 2024) or causal mediation (Imai et al., 2010; Nguyen et al., 2021) that help disentangle the various biological, behavioural, and psychosocial mechanisms underlying

the loneliness-outcome associations are warranted to improve our understanding of the causal pathways. Finally, the study of loneliness and its outcomes will require more attention to the “right” timescale of the underlying processes (Groß & Haffa, 2025) – from hours to years – so that the temporal dynamics and data sampling strategy are better aligned. Future findings drawing on these robust methodologies, in turn, will inform both researchers and policymakers about key intervention targets, ultimately contributing to the prevention of adverse outcomes.

How is Loneliness Transmitted Across Generations?

The negative impacts of loneliness are not restricted to the person experiencing loneliness. For example, parents’ loneliness levels are moderately linked to their offspring’s loneliness in adulthood (Augustijn, 2021; Elovainio et al., 2024; Lobdell & Perlman, 1986), suggesting an intergenerational transmission of loneliness. In other words, loneliness risk often runs within families and across generations. Several mechanisms have been suggested to explain this transmission. For example, parenting practices, such as a lack of positive involvement (Lobdell & Perlman, 1986) and offspring’s mental health problems (Elovainio et al., 2024) may mediate this intergenerational link, for example by shaping attachment orientations which are in turn associated with loneliness in adulthood (Krasko et al., 2025). In addition, parent-child associations persist even when not living in the same household (Augustijn, 2021), suggesting a role of genetic transmission too.

In future, more research examining multiple genetic, behavioural, and psychosocial pathways of intergenerational transmission – both direct and indirect – is warranted. A consideration of complex family influences, such as from children to parents or among siblings, would provide a deeper understanding of family-related transmission of loneliness. More emphasis on structural factors, such as socioeconomic disadvantage early in life, is also needed to address social disparities in loneliness. Finally, future work would benefit from research examining how loneliness relates to family formation, parenthood and related social transitions in adult life.

Reducing Loneliness Effectively

One of the ultimate goals of loneliness research is to identify interventions and policies that can effectively reduce loneliness. Effective interventions need to target theory-informed mechanisms of severe loneliness that work at the individual level, such as social vigilance and withdrawal behaviour (Cacioppo et al., 2014; Qualter et al., 2015), as well as broader societal-level determinants, including social inequalities or exclusion (Barreto et al., 2024). There have been growing efforts to systematically evaluate loneliness interventions (Hickin et al., 2021; Lasgaard et al., 2025; Masi et al., 2011). Several meta-analyses have assessed

the effectiveness of psychosocial interventions across age groups (Eccles & Qualter, 2021; Hickin et al., 2021; Lasgaard et al., 2025; Masi et al., 2011). These reviews generally report small to moderate average effects, but relatively stronger effects for psychological interventions that are designed to address cognition, attention, behaviour, or emotions (Lasgaard et al., 2025), interventions targeting maladaptive social cognition (Masi et al., 2011), and those focused on social-emotional skills training with children and adolescents (Eccles & Qualter, 2021).

However, the current evidence base remains insufficient to provide a unified understanding of what works for whom (and what does not) across diverse populations and contexts. Evidence is also limited regarding the cost-effectiveness of interventions and long-term impacts, which are critical for informing policy and practice. As a result, practitioners in community and government settings are often left to select and deliver programmes without adequate empirical guidance (L. Fried et al., 2020). Addressing those gaps requires a set of priority questions for future research, identified as critical by both researchers and practitioners, to strengthen the evidence base for effective, equitable, and scalable approaches to reducing loneliness across populations.

Understanding What Kind of Interventions Work for Whom and Why

A central question is what interventions work, especially for those experiencing severe or chronic loneliness that might lead to mental and physical health problems (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015; Martín-María et al., 2020; Zhong et al., 2016). Despite acknowledging the importance of addressing severe or chronic loneliness, most intervention studies do not assess or report whether participants were lonely before the intervention. Many studies recruit broad samples (e.g., older adults or individuals with chronic illness or disability) without assessing baseline loneliness. Although intervention outcomes are typically measured with trait-level measures (e.g., UCLA Loneliness Scale) that to some extent reflect prolonged loneliness rather than momentary states, this does not substitute for identifying individuals with severe or chronic loneliness at baseline. More evidence is, therefore, needed to determine whether interventions work for individuals with severe or chronic loneliness or whether targeting individuals experiencing loneliness enhances intervention effectiveness (Lasgaard et al., 2025).

It is also essential to understand not only which interventions work for individuals with chronic loneliness, but also “why” they work. This requires integrating theory into both the design and evaluation of interventions, because theoretical frameworks provide a rationale for targeting key processes underlying chronic loneliness (Goldman et al., 2025). At the same time, evidence from interventions can inform and refine those theories, for instance, demonstrating that cognitive-behavioural therapy designed to shift negative appraisals has a causal role. To advance this integration, a core elements approach is recommended,

which isolates and tests active components of interventions (Käll et al., 2020), rather than evaluating interventions as fixed packages. Identifying which intervention elements, or “active ingredients”, are effective for whom can reveal key mechanisms to target across subgroups.

Another important question is which interventions work for whom. Meta-analyses highlight substantial heterogeneity in intervention effects across studies, suggesting that the same intervention may not equally be effective for everyone and in all circumstances (Eccles & Qualter, 2021; Hickin et al., 2021; Käll et al., 2020; Lasgaard et al., 2025; Masi et al., 2011). This aligns with a growing emphasis in behavioural science on “heterogeneity” in treatment effects (Bryan et al., 2021; Walton et al., 2023). Individuals experiencing loneliness represent a heterogeneous group, with diverse needs and circumstances. Intervention outcomes may therefore depend on how well the intervention strategies (e.g., giving support or cognitive modification), delivery (e.g., online vs. in-person; workplace vs. home) and mode (e.g., individual vs. group-based) match individuals’ needs, resources, and constraints. It is, thus, essential to identify which interventions work best for whom and under what conditions – a question that remains underexplored.

One of the promising future directions is the use of idiographic (personalized) approaches, which recognize that psychological experiences, such as loneliness, are shaped by person-specific processes rather than uniform patterns across individuals (Beck et al., 2025; Kuper et al., 2025). Such approaches require idiographic research designs (both data collection and analysis) that model person-specific processes (Hamaker, 2025). Early empirical applications of idiographic prediction models demonstrated that individuals differ widely in the personal and situational antecedents of feeling lonely, underscoring the value of personalized approaches for more effectively addressing loneliness (Beck & Jackson, 2022).

Are Universal or Targeted Programmes More Effective?

Another key question raised both by researchers and practitioners concerns the relative impact of universal programmes, delivered to whole populations, versus targeted programs, designed for groups at greater risk or with particular characteristics. In other words, is it more effective to invest in population-wide initiatives or to concentrate resources on approaches for those most in need?

On the one hand, the universal programs, such as a community-wide social campaigns open to all residents or interventions aimed at structural and societal factors related to loneliness, can help build social infrastructure and foster a social climate that reaches a broad population. Given that a substantial share of the population report loneliness (16% globally; WHO Commission on Social Connection, 2025), this approach may help individuals across varying levels of loneliness, while also preventing its progression into chronic loneliness (Eccles & Qualter, 2021). To date, however, macro-level programs remain rarely studied,

and recent reviews show a lack of robust evidence on interventions aimed at structural and societal factors (Nyqvist, Coll-Planas, & McHugh Power, 2025).

On the other hand, people experiencing chronic loneliness often face more adverse impacts on health and well-being; and therefore, interventions should prioritize addressing those who are at particular risk to experience chronic loneliness. Not just risk levels, but underlying cases can also differ. For instance, social anxiety or social exclusion may be more relevant for youth, while bereavement and life transitions may be key factors for older adults (Qualter et al., 2015). These differences highlight the need for targeted and tailored strategies. From this perspective, approaches based on the specific needs of different risk groups can be more effective.

Both universal and targeted interventions may be needed for different purposes (e.g., reducing risk of becoming lonely and reducing risk of staying lonely), and they may have synergistic effects. For instance, universal approaches that reach the broader population and shift socio-cultural norms and climates may also benefit at-risk individuals – for example, by fostering more cohesive neighbourhoods or schools. To evaluate effectiveness, a consistent assessment framework is essential, with benefits defined according to the scope of the intervention, for example, strengthening social connection at the community level versus reducing loneliness in specific at-risk groups.

Estimating the Cost-Effectiveness of Interventions

Beyond treatment effects, cost-effectiveness is a critical factor in the planning and implementation of interventions. Evidence on cost-effectiveness can give policymakers confidence to invest in loneliness interventions and help practitioners select the most appropriate approaches. Although still limited, research on the cost-effectiveness of loneliness interventions is increasing, often employing cost-of-illness and cost-utility analyses (L. Engel et al., 2025; Mihalopoulos et al., 2020). Those reviews suggest interventions targeting loneliness are generally cost-effective, although results vary across studies and intervention types. However, there remains a substantial lack of economic evaluations, particularly those embedded in high-quality intervention evaluation designs such as randomized controlled trials, limiting confidence in existing cost-effectiveness estimates (Mihalopoulos et al., 2020).

One important consideration concerns the scope of costs associated with loneliness. Existing estimates focus primarily on health-care expenditures, whereas other costs, such as reduced productivity (Engel et al., 2021) and increased demand for aging-related care (Hanratty et al., 2018; Weiss et al., 2020) have received relatively less attention. Further, evidence on the cost-effectiveness of loneliness interventions has largely centred on older adults, leaving a significant gap for other age groups (Engel et al., 2025; Mihalopoulos et al., 2020). A related priority is to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of interventions that treat

or prevent loneliness earlier in the life course, which may yield benefits across multiple domains. Emerging evidence links loneliness at young ages to downstream outcomes, such as education and employment (Bryan et al., 2021; Juvonen et al., 2000; Matthews et al., 2023; Soest et al., 2020) and civic engagement (Langenkamp, 2021), suggesting that early intervention may avert future costs of loneliness that may exceed the costs of intervention itself.

More research is also needed on comparative cost-effectiveness, including clear rankings, to help practitioners quickly determine the relative value of implementing specific interventions for different populations. A consistent evaluation framework is needed to compare the wide range of intervention types, from individual-level approaches to community infrastructure initiatives and societal level strategies (L. Engel et al., 2025). Such a framework should specify which benefits (e.g., beyond health outcomes and quality of life) and which costs (e.g., including those for volunteers) will be assessed and how those will be measured (McDaid et al., 2017). Another key consideration in comparing interventions is their “use cases” (i.e., the contexts and settings in which they are intended to be implemented), since cost-effectiveness can vary depending on factors such as cultural or national contexts, and on implementation settings (whether aimed at individuals, families, schools, workplaces, neighbourhoods, or society).

Studying the Long-Term Effects of Interventions

Understanding the long-term effects of interventions is critical for resource allocation and evaluating return on investment. Assessing whether interventions can reduce loneliness requires extended follow-up. One recent meta-analysis suggests that long-term effects (i.e., one to six months after the intervention) are comparable to short-term effects (i.e., up to four weeks after the intervention; Lasgaard et al., 2025). However, only a limited portion of evidence included follow-up measures (Eccles & Qualter, 2021; Hickin et al., 2021; Lasgaard et al., 2025) and the “long-term” follow-up ranged from only one to six months, making it difficult to draw conclusions about more persistent effects. Overall, more evidence is needed to determine whether intervention benefits persist beyond the immediate post-intervention period, or produce distal sleeper effects, requiring assessing longer-term follow-up assessments (Lasgaard et al., 2025).

Identifying What Does Not Work

In addition to identifying what works, it is equally important to determine what does not so that resources can be allocated efficiently. Previous meta-analyses have reported that some interventions generally yield relatively small effect sizes. Of course, interventions with weak average effects should not be dismissed outright, as they may be effective for specific subgroups or may show effectiveness when evaluated with different assessment

approaches (e.g., weak short-term effects but stronger long-term effects: sleeper effect). For example, interventions designed to enhance social skills showed weaker average effects in Hickin et al. (2021) and Masi et al. (2011), but relatively strong mean effects for social skills training among youth in Eccles & Qualter (2021). Therefore, more research is needed to clarify which interventions yield inconsistent or weak effects, and *for whom* – particularly in cases where the intervention fails to deliver meaningful benefits for the intended population. Methodologically, statistical approaches such as Bayesian statistics or equivalence tests (Lakens, 2017) allow researchers to conclude that an effect is truly absent.

It is also critical to consider unintended side effects because some interventions may not only be ineffective, but counterproductive and harmful (Foulkes & Andrews, 2023; Foulkes & Stringaris, 2023). For instance, individual-focused interventions that aim to shift thoughts and behaviours (e.g., social skill training) may lead participants to attribute their loneliness to personal deficits, which is often not the case. This might unintentionally heighten stigma of feeling lonely, increasing self-consciousness and social anxiety. Similarly, interventions that rely on parasocial relationships (e.g., with robots or AI) may inadvertently discourage real-world social engagement (Adewale & Muhammad, 2025). Yet, potential side effects have received relatively little attention in the literature and warrant more systematic investigation.

Implications

Addressing the big questions raised above requires changing the way we conduct research on loneliness: We need more and better data on loneliness by implementing studies with smart research designs, valid and culturally sensitive measures, and bigger and more diverse samples representative of the entire population. We also need to expand the “we”, that is, who studies loneliness, by systematically fostering interdisciplinary and international collaborations that include researchers from all continents. And finally, loneliness researchers should contribute to making their research useable for policymakers and other decision makers.

Expanding the Methodological Toolbox

No research method is perfect, yet researchers are often bound to those methods that are dominant in their discipline and in which they have received training. Fields differ to what extent they value and use qualitative versus quantitative, experimental versus observational, or cross-sectional versus longitudinal data. But methodological monotony means that only those questions that can be addressed with certain methods will be studied. For true progress, we need to study all research questions that are relevant, not just those that are convenient, with the methods that are best suited for the research question, not those that we

have grown up with. Most of the next big research topics we have identified in this paper cannot be adequately investigated with the traditional cross-sectional surveys and multiple regression analyses that still dominate the field.

For example, many of the big questions raised above address causal links between variables (e.g., between risk factors and loneliness, between an intervention and loneliness, or between loneliness and a specific societal outcome). Assuming that a central goal of research on loneliness is to provide evidence that can be used for actual real-life changes (whether at the individual or the policy level), this research needs to be designed in a way that it delivers causal conclusions. We encourage loneliness researchers to be transparent and explicit about their causal research objectives (Grosz et al., 2020) and think beyond traditional laboratory experiments and randomized controlled trials and consider other methods for causal inference (Bailey et al., 2024; Rohrer, 2024). Such an expanded toolbox includes, for example, natural experiments and instrumental variable designs (Grosz et al., 2020), advanced panel modelling techniques that focus on within-person processes (Hamaker et al., 2015), causal inference methods that account for various sources of confounding bias (VanderWeele, 2021; VanderWeele et al., 2011), or genetically informed approaches (Hilliard et al., 2024; Liang et al., 2024).

As a second example, another important open question concerns the processes through which loneliness develops within individuals and spreads across people. Again, the traditional cross-sectional survey is inadequate to study these kinds of dynamic processes. Instead, intensive longitudinal studies that enable capturing intraindividual fluctuations in loneliness levels and network studies that allow studying dyads, households or communities over time are needed.

As a third example, policymakers, practitioners and the general public often demand insights into specific subgroups or into long-term trends and their causes, as reflected by questions such as, “How big is the problem in this particular group?”, “Are we lonelier today than in the past?” or “How did the Covid-19 pandemic, the invention of smartphones or some other macro trend change people’s loneliness?” Answering such questions in a scientifically rigorous way requires monitoring loneliness in the entire population, using repeated (ideally longitudinal) designs and samples that are sufficiently representative and large to allow detecting not just of general trends, but also fine-grained analyses of subsets of the population.

In addition, we also need to acknowledge that the causes and processes that trigger and maintain loneliness can be highly idiosyncratic. In addition to developing personalized measurement approaches, idiographic research designs can help elucidate the psychological processes through which individuals become and stay lonely (Beck & Jackson, 2022; Hamaker, 2025; Kuper et al., 2025).

In sum, we can address much more interesting research questions and derive much more robust conclusions by expanding our methodological toolbox. The methods mentioned so far are by no means exhaustive, and it is not our intention to prescribe which methods should or should not be incorporated in this field of research. Rather, we encourage researchers to be open-minded and reflective about different methodological approaches and their benefits and limitations, continue to learn, and collaborate with others to ensure that methodological variety and innovations are picked up in this field. Applying open science principles such as preregistering hypotheses, study designs, and analyses, and sharing data, analyses script files, and materials will ensure transparency and facilitate adoption of innovative methods across disciplines.

Expanding the Database

The demands for better research methods discussed in the previous section have one thing in common: They all require a much larger database than what is currently used in loneliness research. The database could be expanded in two ways: by using existing data in a smarter way, and by establishing systematic and responsive population-based monitoring frameworks.

To facilitate the re-use of existing data, we propose creating open registries documenting loneliness measurement tools, their scoring methods, and datasets that use them. Technical interoperability standards, such as the OMOP Common Data Model and FAIR principles, enable safe linkage across datasets and countries while respecting privacy norms through techniques like differential privacy and federated analysis. One example for such a registry is the Gateway to Global Aging Data (<https://g2aging.org/>) which provides a searchable database of surveys of older adults with harmonized measurement tools.

In addition, data collection efforts need to be scaled up. Population-based longitudinal and repeated cross-sectional monitoring frameworks, in which large representative samples are tracked repeatedly and frequently over longer time spans, would not only enable addressing some of the big research questions discussed above, but they could also be used for systematic evaluation of policies from multiple angles. For instance, measuring loneliness trajectories before and after social media regulation changes could reveal whether platform design modifications reduce social comparison and improve connection quality or whether they reduce social connection by disconnecting vulnerable groups from their lifelines. Similarly, monitoring the loneliness impacts of economic interventions – such as universal basic income pilots or targeted support for lower socioeconomic status communities – could provide crucial evidence for social policy design. Such frameworks could also assess how infrastructure investments (community centres, public transportation, digital access programs) affect social connection across different demographic groups over time.

The European Social Survey (ESS), a Europe-wide repeated cross-sectional survey, offers opportunities for such policy evaluations, although it is limited by reliance on a single-item measure of loneliness. Other large-scale surveys such as the EU Loneliness Survey include standardized multiple-item instruments (Schnepf et al., 2024), but they are designed (and funded) as a one-time survey, with no follow-ups planned so far. There are also ongoing data collections that monitor trends in youth school-based loneliness across multiple countries (Program for International Student Assessment [PISA]) and loneliness in general (Health Behavior in School-aged Children [HBSC]). However, again, those are limited by relying on single-item measures or less commonly used loneliness scales.

Similarly, current longitudinal infrastructure that follows up the same individuals across time and thus enables the examination of within-person processes and causal mechanisms remains inadequate. Where data collection exists, it is often sporadic, age-limited, or poorly harmonized across regions (Goldman et al., 2024; Mahony et al., 2024). For example, the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) represents a unique Europe-wide population-based longitudinal study using multiple standardized loneliness measures, yet its focus on individuals above 50 years limits its ability to examine loneliness trajectories across the entire lifespan. The German Socioeconomic Panel (SOEP) is currently used for the systematic monitoring of loneliness by the German government (Schobin et al., 2024), yet it only includes adult participants and loneliness is only assessed every four years. None of these surveys can be used to, for example, describe or explain long-term trends in loneliness among children and adolescents. In addition, most longitudinal surveys focus on European countries, preventing a truly global perspective.

Finally, combining self-report with behavioural data and administrative registers may add value. Routinely collected administrative data, in turn, offer population-wide coverage, longitudinal depth, and high accuracy for assessing objective indicators, thus enabling a cost-effective examination of multiple life domains, including education, work, health and family. Any use of digital traces and administrative registers must naturally adhere to strict privacy protocols – differential privacy, federated analysis, and user control – to preserve trust and ethical integrity. Strategic reuse enables return-on-investment analyses increasingly demanded by policymakers, linking loneliness outcomes to health records and economic data could therefore help to quantify broader societal benefits of reducing loneliness.

Prioritizing Who is Studied

Although diverse and representative samples are studied in our field, much research still relies on convenience samples, meaning that those populations that are accessible with little effort or costs (e.g., college students) are overrepresented in loneliness research. It is well recognized that conclusions drawn from WEIRD (Western, Education, Industrialized, Rich, Democratic) samples have limited generalizability and that all social science research

should strive to include more diverse and global samples. This is certainly true for loneliness research as well. Future research must integrate perspectives from low- and middle-income countries and culturally diverse populations to challenge prevailing Western-centric assumptions and broaden the scope of understanding.

However, studying large, population-based samples from multiple countries comes at considerable costs and is often not feasible for individual researchers. These challenges could partly be resolved by more collaborative efforts to build large, harmonized databases of secondary data and by large-scale monitoring frameworks that include underrepresented populations (e.g., low and middle-income countries), as discussed in the previous section.

We recognize that resources are limited and collecting such data is often not feasible. When resources are limited, it is particularly important to carefully consider how to spend these resources. When it comes to samples, we suggest that loneliness researchers prioritize studying those populations that are particularly at risk or particularly understudied, rather than those populations that are easily accessible. For example, we could prioritize hard-to-reach populations, those who have to deal with multiple risk factors at once, or those who might potentially experience damage (e.g., to their health) because of loneliness, such as LGBTQ+ individuals, people with migrant background, single parents, people experiencing homelessness, people with chronic illnesses, or residents of nursing institutions. Because identifying and reaching these populations requires more effort and therefore funding than studying university students, these priorities need to be reflected in funding decisions.

Expanding Who Does the Research

Every researcher's thinking is shaped (and limited) by their disciplinary and cultural background. To ensure that these individual limitations do not slow progress, loneliness needs to be studied by people who come from diverse backgrounds. Regarding disciplinary background, we can attest that loneliness is already studied in various disciplines such as psychology, sociology, medicine, urban planning, philosophy, neuroscience and others. However, true inter- or transdisciplinary research is still rare. Regarding cultural background, most loneliness researchers and the populations they study come from high-income countries, whereas low- and middle-income countries are not well represented.

Why would loneliness research benefit from becoming more interdisciplinary and culturally diverse? First, diverse backgrounds foster diverse thinking – the very definition of creativity. Innovative ideas are more likely if people with different backgrounds share their expertise and engage with each other. Second, to ensure that loneliness is conceptualized in a way that captures its entire complexity, different disciplinary and cultural perspectives need to be included (Akhter-Khan et al., 2024). Research that relies on highly narrow conceptualizations of loneliness may produce findings with limited relevance and generalizability beyond a specific cultural context. Third, taking advantage of the different

methodological approaches that dominate specific disciplines will lead to more methodological diversity which can, in turn, inform theory, an important goal in and of itself. Finally, *not* engaging with researchers from other backgrounds may slow down scientific progress. By not knowing or understanding (e.g., due to different terminologies) what others have already done, researchers risk pursuing seemingly innovative ideas that have already been investigated extensively in other fields. In the best scenario, this only leads to redundant research activities and inefficient progress. In the worst case, however, research on loneliness might become so fragmented that an integration of concepts and ideas is no longer possible.

Strengthening interdisciplinary and global research collaborations is no simple task. Language barriers are not only a challenge for researchers from different countries, but also for researchers from different disciplines who, despite communicating in English, use different terminology. To resolve this issue, a structured consensus building process that includes diverse perspectives might help (Leising et al., 2024). Similarly, cultural differences are not just an issue for collaborations among researchers from different countries, but also for researchers from different disciplines, for example with respect to methodological approaches or publication norms. Overcoming these cultural differences requires open-mindedness from all parties and regular opportunities for interaction and exchange. For the field of loneliness research, a first step would be to establish infrastructures and networks that may initiate such exchanges, for example, an international association for loneliness research that offers interdisciplinary conferences and publication outlets and connects loneliness researchers from around the world. Finally, collaborative research that bridges cultural and disciplinary borders is often slower and more expensive than traditional research projects, but it is highly valuable. We therefore call on research funders to support and prioritize these kinds of collaborations.

Making Loneliness Research Useable

Over the past years, public and political attention to the topic of loneliness has thrived. As a result, individuals and organizations in many countries are developing programs aimed at helping people experiencing loneliness, and governments around the world have picked up loneliness as a policy issue (Goldman et al., 2026; Goldman et al., 2024). While this attention to what has once been a niche, even taboo topic is certainly welcome, it bears the risk that programs and policies are developed without a proper scientific foundation.

It is the responsibility of loneliness researchers to make sure that whenever they produce research findings with potential practical or political relevance, that these findings are made accessible and actionable for policymakers and practitioners. This means that it is not sufficient to publish peer-reviewed papers, or, worse, not publish at all. It also means that

researchers cannot just sit and wait for someone (a journalist, a politician, a practitioner) to contact them.

Rather, researchers must make a proactive effort to make their insights available to the broader public. We encourage loneliness researchers to actively engage in science communication, for example via social media, public talks, blogposts, or interviews with the media. In addition, we encourage loneliness researchers to contact policymakers directly whenever they believe they have something relevant to share. Many policymakers welcome input by the scientific community and can be contacted easily via their public email addresses. When communicating with policymakers, we recommend to inform them not just about specific research findings, but also about evidence gaps and how they might be closed with targeted research funding.

However, we also emphasize that science communication needs to be done in responsible ways. This is hard because media (and their audiences) prefer simple, clear messages which are often incompatible with research findings that are nuanced and complex. To reach their audiences, researchers must find the right balance between simplifying their insights to a degree that they can be understood by non-experts and being clear about the nuances and limits of their research.

Conclusion

Over the past decade, loneliness has evolved from a niche topic to a large, interdisciplinary, and impactful research field with broad societal and political relevance. To ensure that research on loneliness delivers the evidence that is necessary to develop effective solutions against loneliness, whether at the individual or the political level, the interests of loneliness researchers must be closer aligned with the needs of policymakers, practitioners, and other decisionmakers. This paper may serve as roadmap guiding future research priorities for both individual researchers and those funding their work.

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